

(Get to know) The RDA Knowledge Base

A Quick Start Guide to Exploration and Use

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1. Introduction

This resource provides a community-friendly overview of the [Research Data Alliance \(RDA\)](https://www.rd-alliance.org)¹ Knowledge Base, conceived and developed through the Horizon Europe funded [RDA TIGER](https://www.rd-alliance.org/working-groups/rda-tiger/)² project, specifically through Work Package 4 (details, credits?). This is intended as a sort of “start here” familiarisation resource for RDA groups and RDA members in general.

The [RDA Knowledge Base \(RDA-KB\)](https://kb-rda.org)³ is a suite of applications and infrastructure that acts as a mechanism for the publication and cataloguing of RDA outputs, supplementary materials, and other useful publications. In addition, it contains, or indexes other resources identified as being useful in an RDA-related context. The RDA-KB aims to improve the quality, usefulness, and maintenance of RDA outputs, and to help users find, use, annotate, and publish RDA-related materials. The RDA-KB also aims to support standardisation in RDA outputs and aligning these outputs with relevant policy in Europe, e.g. EOSC. The Working Group Guidelines for instance, recommend metadata schema and RDA-specific vocabularies.

2. The RDA Knowledge Base Concept

Through the history of the RDA, its corpus has grown organically. Outputs created by working groups (WGs) and interest groups (IGs) have been shared and hosted in a variety of places: the RDA webpages, the RDA Zenodo Community, and on institutional webpages or platforms, etc., with none of these locations hosting a complete library of outputs.

At some point, it was decided that all RDA outputs must be hosted in the RDA Zenodo Community. The Zenodo metadata schema, however, does not include RDA-specific vocabularies. These are important for standardised contextualisation within the RDA e.g., with respect to pathways, stakeholders, groups, etc. This can result in outputs not reaching their intended audience, or if so, with difficulty. **The RDA-KB is intended to remedy this situation through 4 components: the RDA Graph, Discovery, Publisher and Annotator web applications (see fig. 1 below).**

¹ <https://www.rd-alliance.org>

² <https://www.rd-alliance.org/working-groups/rda-tiger/>

³ <https://kb-rda.org>

Figure 1: RDA Applications in the RDA Knowledge Base suite, and its relation to e.g. Zenodo

3. Components of the RDA Knowledge Base

3.1 RDA Graph

The RDA Graph is a consolidated catalogue comprising **disambiguated/de-duplicated** copies of each resource/output. It utilises **RDA-specific vocabularies** for tagging and classification of the resources for more precise RDA-specific descriptions and definitions reflecting the nature, type and targeted use of the output.

The Graph is automatically synchronised with the RDA website and Zenodo, so that it is always up to date. It is the underlying database for connecting and retrieving all these resources, better reflecting the contents of the RDA website, the RDA Zenodo community and wherever RDA resources have been previously published or hosted. In addition, the Graph can be linked to other scientific knowledge graphs⁴, enabling and allowing them to harvest information from each other, thus enriching each other through the resources they host or index.

The Graph is embedded into a set of web-based applications towards supporting discovery, publication and annotation of RDA group outputs, supplementary materials and other resources of interest to the RDA community. It provides a “living view” of what is available.

3.2 RDA Discovery

Through RDA Discovery, users can search for and access all RDA-related resources hosted or referenced in the Graph. It provides dashboard- (see fig. 2 below), and list-type views of all resources, of which there are two types: deposits (created through RDA groups), and annotations (resources that are related to the work of the RDA and RDA groups). **It serves as a single point for finding RDA-related resources.**

There are typical search and discovery features and some that go beyond. **The default dashboard view is interactive, and filters can be applied by selecting any facet in the dashboard graphics, and the relevant results will be reflected in an updated dashboard.** There is a wide variety of facet representations e.g., geographical, chronological, charts, and all facet components are interactive, selectable and cross-linked.

⁴ For example [OpenAIRE Graph](#), [DataCite PID Graph](#), and the [Scholix Graph](#)

Figure 2: Dashboard view of the RDA Discovery Application

As the RDA is a large community, having tools to help with e.g. targeting annotations by specific members are particularly helpful. Searches can also be defined through selecting the type of group, related institutions, people, etc. Thus, the **landing page presents a summary view of the resources available in the RDA corpus** and also **allows a user to instantly “drill down” to resources of interest**. Users can switch between dashboard and list views. In the list view, selecting filters will update the list. Previews of resources show some details, such as abstracts and the deposit link, usually to Zenodo

A particularly useful feature of the discovery application is **saved searches**: the ability to save selected filters and search parameters. If clicked again, these searches will produce updated results. It's an efficient way to access content without having to know in advance what is contained in the RDA-RDA-KB. In addition, **if these saved searches are copied and pasted into a browser, it will take you directly to the updated resource**. You can share your saved searches, so that other members of the RDA (or your group) can directly locate the same resources you have targeted. In this way, you can e.g., tailor and save searches specific to a WG or IG. Find detailed instructions on the use of Discovery.

RDA Publisher

The RDA Publisher provides a curated process whereby RDA groups can publish their work, or other work relevant to the RDA, to Zenodo, the RDA Graph and potentially in future, to other repositories. **The Publisher has several advantages, including the ability to accommodate multiple metadata schema that may depend on the type of content, and to link to any number of LOD-type vocabularies (Linked Open Data) and registries to better contextualise the resources**. This flexibility with respect to metadata schema offers a kind of futureproofing, as it is possible that in future Zenodo may not be the only destination for publication of some types of RDA outputs, for example new formal or specific standards might arise from some groups that are hosted elsewhere. We would want to ensure that these are still findable in a central location, even though they may not be published in Zenodo.

The RDA Graph can be thought of as an additional set of metadata, linked to a platform where these materials are published, usually Zenodo. **The curated publishing workflow serves to minimise or eliminate duplication** of deposits by implementing controlled vocabulary and maintaining consistent metadata across resources so that they are traceable and findable. It also **facilitates quicker publication**. In the case of Recommendations and Supporting Outputs, these are first published to the group outputs page to undergo review, as is the current RDA workflow. Once an output is finalised, publication via the Publisher involves a **two-step process**. One of the group co-chairs submits resources for publication in the relevant RDA Zenodo Community, and a human curator from the RDA Secretariat assesses the resource's readiness. If all is in order, the

resource is published and the co-chairs of the group are notified; if not, the deposit is returned with relevant concerns flagged for revision. Select the PUBLISHER tab to begin depositing your group output.

RDA Annotator

The [RDA Annotator](https://www.kb-rda.org/annotator)⁵ is motivated by the fact that RDA groups invest a lot of time and energy scouring the landscape for input material, working through web-based resources to understand the questions they're trying to answer or to tackle problems they want to solve more fully. In the past, the results of these arduous efforts have not been easily accessible or reusable by others in the community. **The Annotator indexes these resources using RDA vocabulary to link them to pathways, users, group-types etc., then saving them into the Graph so they are searchable and findable within the catalogue of outputs and supplementary materials.**

It works via a browser plugin embedded in the browser toolbar (see fig 3 below), comprising a user-friendly interface and can be invoked for any web resource, allowing users to index them via free-text and vocabulary-based annotation in the Graph.

Once the Annotator browser extension is installed and activated, users can select any snippet of text from website or embedded PDF and send the text to the Annotator with the press of a button next to the cursor. Within the Annotator interface, users can annotate the text with fields for free text, e.g. abstracts, and metadata fields with controlled RDA-related vocabulary, enabling quick overview and findability in the discovery component (see Figure 3). Many of the vocabulary items are optional, and users can save the vocabulary settings they are likely to use often, limiting those that appear when the annotator is invoked.

Select the ANNOTATOR tab to see an overview of how it works, to download the plugin, and to find user manuals and instructions. See [here](#)⁶ for an example annotation.

⁵ <https://www.kb-rda.org/annotator>

⁶ https://kb-rda.org/record/rda_tiger%3ADXSFMWXPHKOGXX3I9HRO0

[Link to D6.2](#)

[RDA ANNOTATOR V1.0.2](#)

Annotations
About
Settings

Resource * ⓘ

Resource Type * ⓘ

Keywords/Tags ⓘ

FAIR-IMPACT ×
Metadata ×
Interoperability ×

RDA Pathways ⓘ

FAIR, CARE, TRUST - Adoption, Implementation, and Deployment
×

GORC Elements ⓘ

Interoperability* ×

Annotate text

The aims and structure of the deliverable...

FAIR-IMPACT aims to support the implementation phase of the [European Open Science FAIR-IMPACT](#) has a focus on the [EOSC Interoperability Framework](#). The perspective for the interoperability for core metadata schemes for research datasets which refers to the ability to share research data across different legal jurisdictions and institutions while complying with relevant policies.

At first, the deliverable illustrates the impact of the [GDPR](#) on legal interoperability in practice. It presents as a landscape analysis the foundation for a legal interoperability framework, by identifying existing widely adopted metadata schemas and controlled vocabularies used in data repositories and their constraints. Their use and implementation are illustrated with specific use cases, highlighting the challenges faced and addressed by different communities.

As a core metadata schema to foster legal interoperability between research datasets the standard stands out as the best-suited tool to describe datasets, facilitates interoperability between portals, and repositories, and allows for the enrichment of metadata in the analysis. Additionally, existing vocabularies support aspects of legal interoperability: international licences (AT-licence), (ODRL), copyright and intellectual property (DCMI, PROV-O), data protection and privacy (GDPR).

Few mappings between metadata schemas are available, they could be improved with more mappings. The ones considered here. The FAIRCore4EOSC has deployed the Metadata Schema and Cross-ontology which, thanks to its ease of access, could enhance the uptake of such mappings effectively.

The recommendation of the DCAT standard as building block for legal interoperability is...

Figure 3: RDA Annotator in action

4. User Support and Sustainability

User support for the RDA Knowledge Base is provided through the Support Materials Drawer and the Helpdesk, which are both accessible via the Knowledge Base webpage in the lower-right corner. Click the “Support” button to access the Support Materials Drawer, including several types of support and guidance on different topics related to the RDA-KB, including user-guides, FAQs, documentation, guidelines for Working Groups, templates, etc (see section 4.1). Click on the “Help” button to submit a query or question relating to the Knowledge Base via the Helpdesk.

4.1 Support Resources and Documentation

The following is a list of example support resources available on the Knowledge Base webpage. All materials can also be found on the [RDA TIGER Zenodo Community](#), under the “Knowledge Base” keyword/subject.

Group Guidance and Support

- Frequently Asked Questions
 - Using the RDA Knowledge Base
 - The RDA Publisher
 - The RDA Annotator
 - Credentials and Authentication

- Working Group Welcome Pack
- Working Group Guidelines
- Preferred Formats for Dissemination and Preservation
- Publication of Outputs

RDA Knowledge Base

- Knowledge Base Documentation
- Annotator Support Documentation
- Publisher Support Documentation

Templates, Systems and Tools

- Templates for Output Reports, Recommendations, Standards and Specifications
- Recommended Metadata Schema
- Vocabularies, Tag Lists and Registries

Additional Resources

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research data sharing without barriers

rd-alliance.org